

CONDITIONS FOR ESTABLISHING AND OPERATING SMALL BUSINESS ENTERPRISES

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Abstract: This article presents ideas and opinions about the conditions for the establishment and operation of small business enterprises and the theoretical aspects of the essence of private entrepreneurship.

Key words: Small business, supply and demand, number of employees, volume of sales.

Introduction

The experience and current trends of economic development in the world and in Ukraine show that it is impossible to move forward without developing various forms of entrepreneurial activity. Entrepreneurship is a special type of economic activity of people. Therefore, entrepreneurship is an economic activity aimed at achieving economic and social results and profit. The concept of "business" is the same business, profession, economic activity aimed at making a profit. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the concepts of "business" and "entrepreneurship" are considered synonymous words. However, the concept of "business" is broader in meaning, as business includes any one-time commercial transactions aimed at earning income in any field of activity. An entity in business is called a businessman or merchant.

Also, in order to overcome the shortcomings of the quantitative approach, the Bolton Committee proposed an "economic" and "statistical" definition of a small firm. By economic definition, small firms are a relatively small segment of the market that includes a firm that; that it is managed personally by the owner (or co-

owners) rather than through a formalized management structure; and firms that meet the three conditions that the firm is independent (i.e., not part of a large enterprise) are included. The conclusion that there is no single definition of small business in world economy and practice is justified.

50 different statistical indicators are used to characterize small enterprises, with priority given to quantitative, in particular, the number of employees, annual turnover and other criteria. Quality criteria are widely used, including profit mass, direct personal contact of management with production staff, customers, suppliers, independence, strict dependence on the nearest markets and sources of raw materials, etc. In many countries, the legal definition of SMEs is that the maximum number of employees is often 50 for SMEs and 200-250 for medium-sized businesses. As for small enterprises, it is usually possible to distinguish micro-enterprises, which usually include small enterprises with less than 10 employees. All US firms are divided into five categories based on the number of employees and the Small Business Administration criteria: smallest (1-24 employees), small (25-99), medium (100-499), large (500-999), very large (1,000 employees or more).

According to statistics, small business is the largest sector of the economy in economically developed countries. In particular, in Germany, 97% of enterprises are small, in other EU countries their share is slightly higher: in Great Britain - 98%, in Spain, France and Italy - 99%. In the most developed countries of the "Big Seven" - the USA and Japan, this share reaches 99%. In 2022, the share of small business and private entrepreneurship in the total number of enterprises in the Republic of Uzbekistan was 87.5% (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. The number of enterprises operating in economic sectors of the Republic of Uzbekistan

If we pay attention to the data presented in Figure 2, the number of enterprises operating in the economic sectors of the Republic of Uzbekistan increased by 327,978 units to 528,929 in 2022 compared to 2010, and the number of small business entities in its structure also increased by 308,265 to 462,834. In this regard, it is worth noting that small business entities made up 76.9 percent of the total enterprises operating in the economic sectors of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2010, and by 2022 this figure was equal to 87.5 percent. This, in turn, represents the result of attention to small business within economic sectors.

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